

Characterizing Timeout Builds in Continuous Integration

Online Appendix

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Appendix A: Advantages and disadvantages of CI services.

The CI process, which includes automated builds, tests, and code quality checks, is supported by various tools like Jenkins,¹ Travis CI,² CircleCI,³ AppVeyor,⁴ and GitHub Actions.⁵ The increase in the adoption of CI practices, as evidenced by the rising proportion of GitHub repositories using CI [1], has led to a proliferation of CI services in the market. This growth also reflects evolving needs for collaborative software development and DevOps practices.

Different CI tools have their advantages and disadvantages, catering to the varied requirements of software projects,⁶ the changing dynamics of DevOps practices [2], and open-source and community support.^{7,8} We review the information available in the official documentation for these popular CI services. Then, we compile a list of advantages and disadvantages for each CI service, as presented in Table A.1.

Table A.1 Advantages and disadvantages of CircleCI, Travis CI, and GitHub Actions

CI provider	Advantages	Disadvantages
CircleCI ⁹	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Support is available for multiple cloud-based hosting services, such as GitHub and GitLab.¹⁰- Self-hostable services are offered, allowing CI to run on one's own servers.¹¹- Promote reusability of CI configurations via Reusable Orbs, which are Shareable configuration packages that can be used to simplify pipeline configurations.¹²	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The cost for projects can scale up quickly with increased usage and parallel builds, while it offers a free tier.¹³- The setup requires extra steps for GitHub projects.¹⁴

¹ <https://www.jenkins.io/>

² <https://www.travis-ci.com/>

³ <https://circleci.com/>

⁴ <https://www.appveyor.com/>

⁵ <https://github.com/features/actions>

⁶ <https://resources.github.com/ci-cd/>

⁷ <https://discuss.circleci.com/>

⁸ <https://github.com/orgs/community/discussions/48283>

⁹ <https://circleci.com/developer>

¹⁰ <https://circleci.com/product/vcs/>

¹¹ <https://circleci.com/pricing/server/>

¹² <https://circleci.com/orbs/>

¹³ <https://circleci.com/pricing/>

¹⁴ <https://circleci.com/docs/getting-started/#prerequisites>

<p>Travis CI¹⁵</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support is available for multiple cloud-based hosting services, such as GitHub and GitLab.¹⁶ - Self-hostable services are offered, allowing CI to run on one's own servers.¹⁷ - Reusability of CI configurations is allowed via shareable configuration snippets.¹⁸ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The cost is high due to the limited free trial.¹⁹ - The setup requires extra steps for GitHub projects.²⁰
<p>GitHub Actions (GHA)²¹</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The cost is generous due to the free minute quota allowed per month.²² - Easy integration for GitHub is available via the "Actions" tab available for GitHub projects.²³ - Reusable workflows can be defined once and can be reused across multiple projects.²⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primarily support is available for GitHub, but less support is available for other cloud-based hosting services.²⁵ - Limited self-hostable facilities are available to allow data privacy and meet specific regulatory requirements while leveraging GitHub Actions for organizations committed to using GitHub.²⁶

¹⁵ <https://docs.travis-ci.com>

¹⁶ <https://docs.travis-ci.com/user/tutorial/#prerequisites>

¹⁷ <https://docs.travis-ci.com/user/enterprise/>

¹⁸ <https://docs.travis-ci.com/user/build-config-imports/>

¹⁹ <https://www.travis-ci.com/pricing/>

²⁰ <https://docs.travis-ci.com/user/tutorial/#to-get-started-with-travis-ci-using-github>

²¹ <https://docs.github.com/en/actions>

²² <https://docs.github.com/en/billing/managing-billing-for-github-actions/about-billing-for-github-actions>

²³ <https://resources.github.com/devops/tools/automation/actions/>

²⁴ <https://docs.github.com/en/actions/using-workflows/reusing-workflows>

²⁵ <https://circleci.com/circleci-versus-github-actions/>

²⁶

<https://docs.github.com/en/actions/hosting-your-own-runners/managing-self-hosted-runners/about-self-hosted-runners>

Appendix B: Re-run experiments when the classes are balanced out.

Balanced classes in datasets are critical for reducing bias towards the majority class, and is particularly important in scenarios where the minority class holds significant interest, such as in fraud detection or rare disease diagnosis. In our case, even though the minority class (timeouts) holds a significant importance, we do not want to introduce an excessive number of false positives. We are interested in modelling the characteristics of builds that are most likely timeouts and not the ones that have some chance of being a timeout. Thus, leaving the class imbalance as it is when creating a model is reflective of the real-world scenarios.

That said, our project selection approach (Section 4 DC-1) addresses the pervasive issue of data imbalance by specifically focusing on the impacted projects. Furthermore, we re-run our experiments in the following two class balancing scenarios to see if there is a substantial change in the results after balancing the classes.

Setup 1. Oversampling with the SMOTE method. In this setup, we use the SMOTE oversampling over our dataset and rebuild the models.

Setup 2. Understanding with the Random method. In this setup, we use the random undersampling over our dataset and rebuild the models.

Table R3C10.1 shows a comparison of AUC and Brier scores of the model trained without class balancing, the model trained with SMOTE-over-sampled dataset, and the model trained with random-under-sampled dataset.

Table R3C10.1 AUC and Brier scores of the models with different sampling methods

Model	AUC	Brier scores
The model trained without class balancing	0.939 with an optimism value of 0.0001	0.008 with an optimism value of -0.0002
The model trained with SMOTE-over-sampled dataset (Setup 1)	0.966 with an optimism value of 0.0000	0.071 with an optimism value of 0.0000
The model trained with random-under-sampled dataset (Setup 2)	0.940 with an optimism value of -0.0021	0.098 with an optimism value of -0.0021

From the table, we observe that AUC values do not change substantially, but the brier score shows a slight increase in the case of over sampling as well as in the case of under sampling. In particular, brier scores are used to assess the accuracy of probabilistic predictions. A Brier score is a measure where lower values indicate more accurate predictions. The brier score in setup 1 indicates less accuracy compared to the first model, while the brier score in setup 2 is the least accurate among the three. Thus, we use the model without any class balancing in the rest of our study.

Appendix C: Projects we used for the model

Project Number	Project Name
P1	docker-atlassian-confluence/cptactionhank
P2	android-branch-deep-linking-attribution/Branch...
P3	onyx/onyx-platform
P4	atlasdb/palantir
P5	docker-atlassian-jira/cptactionhank
P6	helios/spotify
P7	docker-atlassian-jira-software/cptactionhank
P8	onyx-kafka/onyx-platform
P9	web-branch-deep-linking-attribution/BranchMetrics
P10	influxdb/influxdata
P11	cloudify-manager/cloudify-cosmo
P12	monod/TailorDev
P13	client/keybase
P14	ok/okpy
P15	autoreject/autoreject
P16	libnetwork/moby
P17	coala/coala
P18	kapacitor/influxdata
P19	meteor-on-fhir/clinical-meteor
P20	linuxbrew-core/Homebrew

P21	protractor/angular
P22	tikv/tikv
P23	swarmkit/docker
P24	tendermint/tendermint

Appendix D: Statistical model after removing P1.

Design

Below, we illustrate the graphs related to the study design and our actions.

MF-1 Mitigate collinearity

Fig. F.1 Hierarchical clustering of features based on Spearman's rank correlation (ρ). The dotted line shows $\rho = 0.7$. We remove insertions, files, lines added to the related files, lines added to any file, lines deleted from the related files, and lines deleted from any file.

MF-2 Mitigate multicollinearity

```
redun(formula = frmla, data = df22, r2 = 0.9, nk = 0)
```

```
n: 103394  p: 13  nk: 0
```

```
Number of NAs: 0
```

```
Transformation of target variables forced to be linear
```

```
R-squared cutoff: 0.9  Type: ordinary
```

```
R2 with which each variable can be predicted from all other variables:
```

queued_month	queued_day	queued_hour	queued_min
0.002	0.012	0.018	0.016
most_recent_label	most_recent_duration	timeout_ratio	deletions
0.128	0.013	0.470	0.575
loc	author_tendency	files_tendency	changes_to_related_files
0.626	0.449	0.434	0.391
changes_to_any_file			
0.599			

```
No redundant variables
```

Applying redun to our set of features did not identify any additional features for exclusion.

MF-4 Allocate DoF.

Fig. F.2. Dotplot showing the Spearman multiple ρ^2 of each feature and the likelihood of a timeout build.

From the figure, we observe that the recent build status, timeout ratio, author tendency, file tendency, and recent build duration have higher ρ^2 values than the other features. Thus, we allocate three DoF for those features except for the status of the most recent build since it is a binary feature.

Results

Below, we describe our results.

Model Fitness

		Model Likelihood		Discrimination		Rank Discrim.	
		Ratio Test		Indexes		Indexes	
Obs	103394	LR chi2	4750.91	R2	0.425	C	0.931
0	102364	d.f.	18	R2(18,103394)	0.045	<u>Dxy</u>	0.861
1	1030	Pr(> chi2)	<0.0001	R2(18,3059.2)	0.787	gamma	0.865
max deriv	200			Brier	0.007	tau-a	0.017

	Coef	S.E.	Wald Z	Pr(> Z)
Intercept	-8.3702	0.2154	-38.86	<0.0001
queued_month	0.0068	0.0106	0.65	0.5188
queued_day	0.0316	0.0211	1.50	0.1345
queued_hour	-0.0131	0.0055	-2.40	0.0164
queued_min	0.0032	0.0021	1.55	0.1211
most_recent_label	2.7023	0.0968	27.92	<0.0001
most_recent_duration	0.1986	0.0196	10.11	<0.0001
most_recent_duration'	-0.2472	0.0246	-10.04	<0.0001
timeout_ratio	201.7162	11.1195	18.14	<0.0001
timeout_ratio'	-960.4247	56.1931	-17.09	<0.0001
deletions	0.0000	0.0000	-0.37	0.7111
loc	0.0000	0.0000	-0.05	0.9595
author_tendency	0.4132	0.1161	3.56	0.0004
author_tendency'	-6.0237	1.6956	-3.55	0.0004
author_tendency''	9.2701	2.6171	3.54	0.0004
files_tendency	0.0164	0.0127	1.29	0.1953
files_tendency'	-0.0704	0.0515	-1.37	0.1717
changes_to_related_files	0.0000	0.0001	0.29	0.7697
changes_to_any_file	0.0000	0.0000	0.30	0.7669

The discriminatory power and calibration of our model are excellent (AUC of 0.931 and Brier score of 0.007). Moreover, the fit is highly stable across different bootstrap samples (mean optimism values of 1.055524e-03 and -3.808353e-05 for AUC and Brier score, respectively), suggesting that the interpretation of our model will produce meaningful results.

Feature Importance

Table F.1 Importance of families

Family		Overall	Nonlinear
Build history	D.F.	5	2
	χ^2	2449.86***	435.28***
Timeout tendency	D.F.	5	3
	χ^2	19.04**	14.19**
Queued time	D.F.	4	-
	χ^2	11.70*	-
Author experience	D.F.	2	-
	χ^2	0.2 ^o	-
Size	D.F.	2	-
	χ^2	0.18 ^o	-
Entire model (all families)	D.F.	18	5
	χ^2	3550.30***	594.22***

^o $p \geq 0.05$; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Fig. F.3. (a) Timeout ratio vs. the probability of builds timing out and (b) Build duration vs. the probability of timing out.

Timeout builds are strongly associated with the project build history, while author experience, and size are the most weakly associated families with timeout builds.

Appendix E: MF-1 Mitigate collinearity - Reasons for choosing one feature over the other when $\rho > 0.7$.

Fig. E.1 Hierarchical clustering of features based on Spearman's rank correlation (ρ)

Fig. E.2 **Case 1**

In this scenario, we're addressing multicollinearity in our model by selecting variables that provide the most detailed information. When comparing "files" and "insertions," which have a correlation coefficient (ρ) greater than 0.7, we opt for "insertions." This choice is made because the number of insertions offers more detailed insights into each commit than the mere count of files modified. Consequently, we eliminate "files" in favor of "insertions."

Similarly, when evaluating "insertions" against "lines of code (loc)," both of which also have a ρ greater than 0.7, we decide to retain "insertions" and remove "loc." This decision is based on the fact that the number of insertions provides specific information about each commit, whereas the "loc" might not vary significantly across commits.

Fig. E.3 **Case 2**

These are author-specific features. From these three features, we can keep only one. We will keep the "changes to any file" feature because it captures the overall experience (to date) of the developer about the project.

Fig. E.4 **Case 3**

Similar to Case 2, these are also author-specific features. The difference is that here we capture the author's prior experience in working on the files modified in the commit under analysis.

From these three features, we can keep only one. We will keep the "changes to released files" feature because it captures the overall experience of the developer about the files linked to a certain commit.

Appendix F: MF-4 Allocate DoF

Fig. F.1 Dotplot showing the Spearman multiple ρ of each feature and the likelihood of a timeout build

Appendix G: Analysis of the `no_output_timeout` feature.

Design

In CircleCI, the set time limit, controlled by the `no_output_timeout` parameter, may play a role in reducing build timeout occurrences. For example, the #1656 issue in the `parse-community/Parse-SDK-iOS-OSX` project shows that increasing the default time limit from ten minutes to 60 minutes has mitigated CI timeouts. In fact, developers have the flexibility to increase this limit, potentially reducing the likelihood of timeouts.

To evaluate the importance of the `no_output_timeout` value, we add the value as a feature to our regression analysis. We use a default of ten minutes for builds where this parameter is not explicitly set. Then, we refit our regression model.

Results

We find that this feature does not provide a statistically significant amount of explanatory power. Indeed, The table below provides an overview of the importance scores for the features in our new model, which includes the `no_output_timeout` feature.

Table G.1 The feature importance of our new model with the `no_output_timeout` feature.

Family	Feature		Overall	Nonlinear
Build history	Recent build status	DF χ^2	1 1,208.19 ***	- -
	Timeout ratio	DF χ^2	2 708.85 ***	1 270.29 ***
	Recent build duration	DF χ^2	2 126.71 ***	1 121.77 ***

Timeout tendency	Author tendency	DF χ^2	3 11.13 *	2 10.71 **
	File tendency	DF χ^2	2 9.28 **	1 8.59 **
Queued time	Queued month	DF χ^2	1 3.09 °	
	Queued day	DF χ^2	1 2.60 °	
	Queued hour	DF χ^2	1 1.35 °	
	Queued minute	DF χ^2	1 0.67 °	
Author experience	Changes to related files	DF χ^2	1 1.86 °	
	Changes to any file	DF χ^2	1 0.36 °	
Size	Deletions	DF χ^2	1 0.12 °	
Build Configuration	No output timeout	DF χ^2	1 0.06 °	
Entire Model (All features)		DF χ^2	18 4,234.03 ***	5 596.71 ***

° $p \geq 0.05$; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Appendix H: Choice of statistical modelling over traditional machine learning

The reason behind the choice of statistical modelling over traditional machine learning is that our goal is to characterize timeout builds and not to predict. Since statistical models, such as logistic regression, provide clear insights into how different factors influence outcomes,²⁷ We decided to use a statistical model in our analysis. Indeed, unlike other traditional machine learning methods, a decision tree would also provide insights into how various attributes split at each node, offering a clear and intuitive visualization of the decision-making process. To take this into account, we build a decision tree to visualize our data as shown below (Fig. R3C12.1). We limit the number of levels in the tree to limit memorization of data.²⁸

Fig. R3C12.1: Decision Tree.

This decision tree is also consistent with our observation that build history and timeout tendency features are the most important features that characterize timeout builds. However, this visualization neither provides insight into how much each family of features describe the probability of timeout builds nor an order of importance. Our study needs more analysis than visualization. Thus, we keep to statistical modelling in our manuscript, and we discuss any bias that may be introduced due to the choice of statistical models in our threats to validity section as an internal threat.

²⁷ <https://www.fharrell.com/post/stat-ml/>

²⁸ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/tree.html>

Appendix J: Different fixes used by developers to avoid CI timeouts.

- **Disabling extensive tests.** This strategy involves selectively turning off certain long-running or non-critical tests within a project's test suite to reduce the overall time taken for the build process, thus preventing timeouts. For example, in the `cptactionhank/docker-atlassian-confluence` project, the developers commented out a few integration tests.²⁹ Similar cases were found in other projects, such as `onyx-platform/onyx`³⁰ and `cptactionhank/docker-atlassian-jira-software`.³¹ This approach helps in focusing on tests that are essential for the current build, while potentially deferring others to be run less frequently or under specific conditions.
- **Increasing the `no_output_timeout` setting.** This strategy extends the build duration without any output before the build is automatically terminated as a timeout. For instance, in the `autoreject/autoreject` project,³² the developers increase the `no_output_timeout` from the default value of ten minutes to two hours. We observe similar changes to the `no_output_timeout` setting in other projects, such as `influxdata/influxdb`³³ and `coala/coala`.³⁴ While this adjustment allows for longer-running tasks within the build process to be completed without being timed out, accommodating processes that naturally take more time to produce output, this fix is not always optimal because each project using CircleCI is billed according to their use of “build minutes” on the service. Increasing the time limit would increase service usage.
- **Restarting the build.** This strategy is employed by manually or automatically triggering a new CI build process if the previous one fails due to a timeout. For example, the developers in the `influxdata/kapacitor` project³⁵ wanted to restart the build run when a CircleCI timeout was observed. Similar situations were also observed in other projects (e.g., `oppia/oppia`³⁶). However, restarting builds can sometimes lead to unnecessary resource consumption if the underlying issue causing the timeout is not addressed [3].
- **Adding log outputs.** Implementing logging to minimize the time without output in CircleCI involves strategically inserting log statements within the build process to

²⁹

<https://github.com/cptactionhank/docker-atlassian-confluence/commit/e81db60ee6cbee71bb427aa015afb3b9762d029c>

³⁰ <https://github.com/onyx-platform/onyx/commit/32147f45efaeff6e0e52dc04f6507016d7ffb160>

³¹

<https://github.com/cptactionhank/docker-atlassian-jira-software/commit/bcb92b6dba461ea4010615f72f88d88025d5bff6>

³²

<https://github.com/autoreject/autoreject/pull/194/commits/92b388594d3c1cb2678c1f189940b84cfc9b9f5c>

³³ <https://github.com/influxdata/influxdb/commit/19dcebc730cceb9948857d5e7a6ca57fc844efdf>

³⁴ <https://github.com/coala/coala/pull/2204/commits/bad66f53324d4dafd0140f2ef42f928d501abe6c>

³⁵ <https://github.com/influxdata/kapacitor/pull/604>

³⁶ <https://github.com/oppia/oppia/issues/7646>

generate regular feedback, reducing the likelihood of hitting the `no_output_timeout` limit. For example, the developers in the `linuxbrew/homebrew-test-bot` project³⁷ add dots (".") to log output to provide continuous feedback during its execution. These dots indicate ongoing progress without necessarily adding detailed log information while avoiding overwhelming the logs with too much irrelevant information; this approach helps to keep the build process within the CircleCI environment from timing out due to inactivity.

In addition to the above, we find specific attempts that are tailored to the project made by developers to mitigate timeouts. For example, the developers in the `BranchMetrics/android-branch-deep-linking-attribution` project³⁸ identified that emulator version 23 was causing endless hangs in their CircleCI builds, while version 22 did not exhibit the same issue. To address this, a pull request was initiated aiming to update the tests to utilize emulator version 22 instead.

³⁷ <https://github.com/Linuxbrew/homebrew-test-bot/pull/80>

³⁸ <https://github.com/BranchMetrics/android-branch-deep-linking-attribution/pull/400>

References

- [1] M. Golzadeh, A. Decan, and T. Mens, “On the rise and fall of CI services in GitHub,” in *2022 IEEE International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution and Reengineering (SANER)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 662–672.
- [2] G. Kim, J. Humble, P. Debois, J. Willis, and N. Forsgren, *The DevOps Handbook: How to Create World-Class Agility, Reliability, & Security in Technology Organizations*. IT Revolution, 2021.
- [3] R. Maipradit, D. Wang, P. Thongtanunam, R. G. Kula, Y. Kamei, and S. McIntosh, “Repeated builds during code review: An empirical study of the OpenStack community,” in *2023 38th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (ASE)*, IEEE, Sep. 2023. doi: 10.1109/ase56229.2023.00030.